

Grating integration technologies for edge emitting AlGaAs diode lasers

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Diode lasers for sensing applications require optical spectra with defined center wavelengths, narrow linewidths and reduced thermal shift with current induced internal heating. To achieve this Bragg gratings have to be integrated into the diode laser cavity. In this work we discuss two ebeam based processing technologies that allow the monolithic integration of Bragg gratings into high-power edge emitting AlGaAs lasers ($\lambda = 760 \text{ nm} \dots 1120 \text{ nm}$) without considerably degrading the laser efficiency and power.

One grating technology starts with a partial growth of the vertical laser structure with MOVPE. After the wet chemical etching of shallow grating lines into high etch contrast GaAsP/ InGaP grating layers, the vertical structure is completed in the same MOVPE reactor. The production of overgrown gratings (OG) with highly defined dimensions is possible because the gratings are defined by epitaxial layers. However, due to the fast propagation velocity of crystal defects in the AlGaAs material system the overgrowth needs special attention. Moreover, contamination with oxygen has to be avoided during grating preparation and overgrowth, since the resulting deep-level traps promote non-radiative recombination and degrade the laser efficiency. Therefore the vertical structure design avoids aluminum containing layers (which are prone to oxygen incorporation) close to the overgrowth surface. Examples of OG are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The InGaP grating lines in Fig. 1 have a period to grating line ratio (PTG) of $140 \text{ nm} / 70 \text{ nm}$ and are surrounded by GaAs confinement layers. The grating has a coupling coefficient $\kappa > 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ as it is required for short grating bursts in sampled grating DBR lasers [1]. Fig. 2 shows GaAs grating lines surrounded by AlGaAs (PTG $320 \text{ nm} / 80 \text{ nm}$). A continuous InGaP layer below the grating lines prevents the lower AlGaAs from exposure to air during the manufacturing and overgrowth process. These gratings are applied for instance to small linewidths 1064 nm DFB lasers which require a defined and small $\kappa < 1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [2].

Another integration technology uses surface gratings (SG) deeply etched into the full vertical laser structure. An 800 nm thick Ti/nLoF hard mask is patterned and transferred into p-cladding and confinement layers. Dependent on the vertical structure the gratings are transferred with BCl_3/Ar reactive ion etching (RIE) up to $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ deep into the wafer surface. For a stable process higher order gratings with periods of several 100 nm are preferred since the aspect ratio can be minimized while the reflectivity can remain high by proper grating design. Prerequisites for a high reflectivity of such gratings are (i) a precise control of the etch depth of the grating grooves and (ii) a vertically V-shaped profile towards the optical active region [3]. Fig. 3 shows a SG with $1.3 \mu\text{m}$ deep grooves as it is applied for instance to DBR laser arrays [4].

On the conference we will discuss advantages and disadvantages of the studied grating integration technologies and present applications, where monolithic gratings have been successfully applied to AlGaAs diodes lasers.

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Fig. 1. OG with InGaP grating lines embedded in GaAs (PTG of $140 \text{ nm} / 70 \text{ nm}$)

Fig. 2. OG with GaAs grating lines and InGaP protection layer embedded in AlGaAs (PTG $320 \text{ nm} / 80 \text{ nm}$)

Fig. 3. SG with $1.3 \mu\text{m}$ deep V-shaped grooves (PTG at the top $420 \text{ nm} / 150 \text{ nm}$ and at the bottom $420 \text{ nm} / 30 \text{ nm}$)